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ANALYSIS OF WORD FREQUENCY EFFECT ON NATIVE
AND NON-NATIVE ENGLISH SPEAKERS

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Lexical decision task is a common technique for investigating word recognition. It is a procedure used in many psychology and psycholinguistics experiments. The basic procedure involves measuring how quickly people classify stimuli as words or nonwords.

Some features can influence the speed at which one responds to the word. One of the most important features in lexical decision tasks is word frequency. That is why the present experiment aimed to investigate the word frequency effect on both native and non-native English speakers.

A total of 3 participants took part in our experiment: one native English speaker and two non-native English speakers. All the participants agreed to have their data analyzed and reported.

The first factor we manipulated was word frequency. This factor has two levels: high-frequency level and low-frequency level.

The second factor we manipulated was the language nativeness of subjects and its levels: native English speakers and non-native English speakers.

The dependent variable in our experiment is word reaction time.

In the present experiment, we used 80 words in English: 20 high-frequency words, 20 low-frequency words and 40 pseudowords.

All high-frequency and low-frequency words were taken from the MRC Psycholinguistic Database. The word's frequency of occurrence was taken in the norms of Kucera and Francis. The mean frequency of occurrence of high-frequency words is 261, whereas the mean frequency of occurrence of low-frequency words is 1. Both high-frequency and low-frequency words are nouns that consist of 7 phonemes, 2 – 3 syllables and 7 – 9 letters.

Pseudowords were generated by means of a multilingual pseudoword generator Wuggy, with taken high-frequency and low-frequency words as input data.

The lexical decision task was organized as a series of consecutive trials each participant had to do.

Experimental stimuli were computerized using PsychoPy. The lexical decision task was created so that subjects could read instruction at the beginning of the experiment and then were shown one stimulus at a time. The duration of one stimulus being on the screen was set as 20 seconds. All the words were shown randomly.

The experiment was conducted on a personal computer in person. Each subject sat down at a table in front of a computer screen and started his trial after having carefully read the instruction. Each trial consisted of a fixation cross

followed by a word appearance and the subject's response on it. Subjects had to decide as quickly as possible whether the strings of letters that appeared on the screen were words or pseudowords by pressing the "right arrow" or the "left arrow" on the keyboard correspondingly, without using any supplementary materials.

We excluded from the data analysis all the responses that took the subject more than 5 seconds, as well as wrong responses. This accounted for 27% of the total number of responses given.

Having analyzed all the data of the experiment conducted, we found out that the mean reaction time of high-frequency words across both native and non-native English speakers is shorter than the mean reaction time of low-frequency words. The mean reaction time of native English speakers is 0,69 sec. for high-frequency words and 0,85 sec. for low-frequency words; and the mean reaction time of non-native English speakers is 1,07 sec. for high-frequency words and 2,9 sec. for low-frequency words. It means that the response for high-frequency words is faster than the response for low-frequency words, because we retrieve and process high-frequency words faster than the low-frequency ones.

Both native and non-native speakers also processed and responded to words faster than pseudowords. The mean reaction time of native English speakers is 0,73 sec. for words and 0,80 sec. for pseudowords; and the mean reaction time of non-native English speakers is 1,46 sec. for words and 1,72 sec. for pseudowords. We can explain it by the fact that in order to understand whether it is a word or a pseudoword, a subject needs to try to encode the stimulus as a high-frequency or low-frequency word first, so it takes more time to understand that this is a non-existing word.

According to the data obtained, frequency does have a larger effect on non-native speakers, and we have also received the data that the reaction time needed for non-native English speakers is about twice larger than the time needed for native English speakers to process the word. In our opinion, it is influenced by the language proficiency level of the participants, who took part in the present experiment.

To sum up, we can conclude that: native English speakers respond faster to high-frequency words than to low-frequency words; non-native English speakers also respond faster to high-frequency words than to low-frequency words; the reaction time for words is shorter than the reaction time for pseudowords both for native English speakers and non-native English speakers; reaction time of both high-frequency and low-frequency words, as well as words and pseudowords, taken by native English speakers, is shorter than the reaction time of the same words taken by non-native English speakers.